

Results and Discussion

The reaction is attended with an induction period and then follows first order rate law. First order plots were obtained for about 70% of the reaction. Under the conditions used, the oxidising species of Chromium (VI) is HCrO_4^- . The rate is first order with respect to methyl ester of 3-phenyl acrylic acid (Table 1) and hydrogen ions (Table 2).

TABLE 1. VARIATION OF RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF METHYL ESTER OF 3-PHENYL ACRYLIC ACID

$10^3 [\text{Cr(VI)}] = 5.0M$; $[\text{H}^+] = 2.0M$; Temp. = 30°

$10^2 [\text{Ester}]$ moles litre ⁻¹	$10^5 k_1 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$10^3 k_1$ [Ester]
1.0	4.72	4.72
1.5	7.32	4.88
2.0	9.85	4.93
2.5	11.95	4.78

TABLE 2. VARIATION OF RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF HYDROGEN IONS

$10^3 [\text{Cr(VI)}] = 5.0M$; $10^2 [\text{Ester}] = 2.0M$; Temp. = 30°

$[\text{H}^+]$ moles litre ⁻¹	$10^5 k_1 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$10^5 k_1$ [H ⁺]
1.2	4.77	3.97
1.6	6.17	3.83
2.0	7.92	3.97
2.4	9.75	4.07

The results on the effect of manganous ions given in Table 3 have shown following characteristic features of the reaction. (a) The induction period in the early stages of the reaction is eliminated. (b) In the presence of manganous ions the rate is decreased nearly to one third of the rate, after the induction period, in the absence of manganous ions. (c) The rate in the presence of manganous ions is nearly the same as the rate in the early parts of the induction period.

TABLE 3. EFFECT OF MANGANOUS IONS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

$10^2 [\text{Ester}] = 2.0M$; $10^3 [\text{Cr(VI)}] = 5.0M$
 $[\text{H}^+] = 2.0M$; Temp. = 30°

$10^4 [\text{Mn}^{++}]$ moles litre ⁻¹	$10^5 k_1 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
—	9.85
4.0	3.68
8.0	2.90
12.0	2.47
16.0	2.12

The behaviour of Mn(II) in the reaction is complex, but it probably shows that some intermediate species

of chromium, Cr(V) or Cr(IV)^{5,7,8} oxidises the ester and that the Mn(II) removes the induction period by reacting with Cr(VI) and producing this intermediate species. The reaction of this intermediate species with the ester is probably inhibited by Mn(II). A similar behaviour is found⁹ in the oxidation of oxalate by permanganate.

A plot of $\log k_1$ versus inverse of absolute temperature (Table 4) gives a straight line. Arrhenius equation is therefore valid. The energy of activation (E), the heat of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) for the overall reaction, calculated from the data given in Table 4 have values 17 Kcals mole⁻¹, 16.4 K.cals mole⁻¹ and -15 cal mole⁻¹ degree⁻¹ respectively. The value of free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) at 30° is found as 21.0 K cal mole⁻¹.

TABLE 4. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON RATE

$10^2 [\text{Ester}] = 2.0M$; $[\text{H}^+] = 2.0M$;
 $10^3 [\text{Cr(VI)}] = 5.0M$

Temperature °K	$10^5 k_1 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
303	7.52
308	12.43
313	15.53
318	24.50

The value of entropy of activation found was higher than the value reported by previous workers¹⁰ for 3-phenyl acrylic acid. This might be due to some influence of inductive effects of $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ group as compared to $-\text{COOH}$ group and of solvent composition on the rate. Further, the mechanism suggested is also different.

The oxidation of styrene by CrO_2Cl_2 exhibit an isotope effect which suggests that the rate determining step produces a carbonium ion¹¹. On the other hand, the isotope effects observed in the oxidation of cinnamic acid by acid permanganate are more consistent with the formation of a cyclic ester².

It is believed that chromic acid oxidation of olefinic compounds probably involves $[\text{HCrO}_3]^+$ as the active oxidant species¹. If $[\text{HCrO}_3]^+$ were the active oxidant species in the present case, the rate would depend on the square of the hydrogen ion concentration. The fact that the rate depends only on the first power of the concentration of hydrogen ions (Table 2) would require that the active oxidant species is H_2CrO_4 :

The rate determining step is

and this is followed by a number of fast steps in which intermediate products of ester are oxidized.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. A. Thaker, Professor and Head, University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar, for providing necessary laboratory facilities and to Dr. G. V. Bakore, Professor and Head, University Department of Chemistry, Udaipur University, Udaipur, for giving inspiration throughout the work.

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